

REGARDING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL CRITERIA AND FACTORS OF ORIGIN OF CONFLICTS BETWEEN YOUNG PEOPLE

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***Abstract** In this article, the conflicts that arise during adolescence, the factors of their occurrence, the interests, needs, views, etc. between the parties in interpersonal relations. Problems such as the origin of conflicts and the emergence of conflicts based on these conflicts, as well as social empowerment and social empowerment are highlighted.*

***Keywords** Adolescence, conflicts, interests, needs, social reinforcement, social reinforcement, conflict group integration.*

We will reflect on this period and its specific aspects. Adolescence is a unique period of a person's life, in which psychological conditions such as the rapid development of secondary sexual organs, changes in body structure, the formation of self-perceptions, and an increase in maximalism in relation to the external environment are observed. The most difficult stage of childhood is adolescence. During this period, the child experiences a transitional stage, that is, the transition from childhood to adulthood.

Another characteristic characteristic of adolescence is the observation of conflict situations. Adolescent conflicts are very different from conflicts at other times. We will try to study the psychological characteristics of the observed conflicts between them, which are typical until the period of adolescence.

It is one of the urgent issues of our time to research this uniqueness, to study the conflicts observed in teenagers based on these situations. When defining conflicts, we pay special attention to their conflicting aspects, that is, the interests, needs, views, etc. between the parties. causes contradictions, and conflicts arise

based on these contradictions. However, at this point, the question of exactly what kind of opposition can be called a conflict is relevant. And this naturally goes back to the issue of their psychological criteria. We will address these criteria below. According to a group of scientists, it is necessary to pay attention to the following situations when solving this problem (2,3,4):

- 1) interdependence of the parties, that is, both parties are interdependent, the activity of one person ensures the actions of the second person, and these actions call for the response reactions of the first subject, and h. in this way, the interaction of the parties occurs, their control is observed, but if there are strict rules of communication (for example, a boxer's fight), this is not a conflict;
- 2) awareness of the conflict of the situation, that is, one side or both sides evaluate the actions of others as hostile actions aimed at destroying the achievement of desired goals or fighting;
- 3) choosing the strategy of the second behavior: seeking compromise or a solution that is acceptable to both parties, or escalating the conflict, intensifying the struggle, for example, moving from the struggle of points of view (cognitive conflict) to the struggle of individuals (interpersonal conflict), then to the struggle of groups and reaping excellence.

There are no guilty parties or rights in the conflict, everyone wants to achieve their goals. Conflict is a type of interaction in which the outcome affects all participants in the conflict, each person contributes to the conflict. However, usually a person thinks: "The conflict is not mine, the other person is to blame", "I am right, and the other person is wrong, he is bad", and each person gathers allies around him to prove his right. This is how the conflict escalates.

The outcome of the conflict is not always the same. The dispute will end by itself in the case of agreement between the parties or in the case of one of the parties withdrawing from the conflict, as well as in the case of reconciliation due to the intervention of third parties.

As noted above, conflict is an exaggerated form of contradictions, but at the same time, it serves as a way of identifying and resolving contradictions. In this

sense, the question arises: what causes the conflict, what are the stages of its development? It can be answered as follows: the conflict is caused by an objective life situation created by the opposite parties, and these parties themselves have certain interests, needs, and goals. Naturally, the non-recognition of some needs of one side by the other forms the socio-psychological basis of the conflict. This itself is a structure of contradictions, and it creates a conflict situation that has not turned into a conflict. Thus, a conflict situation is such a complex of human needs and interests that creates the ground for a real struggle between different social subjects.

The subject of the dispute is such a fundamental contradiction that the parties enter into a struggle for this reason and to resolve this contradiction.

During the conflict, as the disagreement is resolved, a way out of the impasse is sought, and then the question of the function of the conflict is raised - positive or negative, good or bad. In other words, is conflict good or bad? Here, from our usual point of view, we give a causal answer, because the conflict always takes the form of family quarrels and disagreements, service anxieties, inter-ethnic, territorial, socio-political antagonisms, sufferings and losses. Based on this, it has become a habit to look at the conflict as a negative event.

However, if you look closely at the essence of this problem, you will see a different perspective, a different ageism. Based on this, the conflict can be considered not only a negative social phenomenon, but also a positive one. Our opinion here is as follows: indeed, conflict is an unpleasant, unwanted phenomenon that begins to erode a normally functioning social system, but in the course of the conflict, such forces appear that can restore peace and tranquility to the system, as well as keep it in a stable state.

Along with this, there is also a view of the conflict as a deviation from the norm, contrary to the mood of viewing it as a norm of social relations, a normal state of society.

Carrying out a motivational analysis of controversial behavior, P. I. Ilin emphasizes that a conflict is such an interaction between two parties that the realization of the goals of one party contradicts the goals of the other party, that is,

competition appears as an objective situation, and on the other hand, emotional-emotional dislike of the other person, the mood of competitive interaction between people, their various psychological characteristics cause conflicting behavior. While conflicts are inevitable in human interaction, they can also serve a positive constructive function:

- the conflict, denying stagnation, gives impetus to a certain movement towards the past;
- in the course of the conflict, the object of the source of disagreement occurs and it becomes possible to resolve it, to "remove" it, to find means to prevent future conflicts;
- conflict is a way of self-affirmation, especially in teenagers, a form of behavior necessary to maintain status in a conflict group.
- conflict within the group in scientific activity creates the level of tension necessary for creative activity; therefore, the research showed that the productivity of creative scientific activity is higher in conflicted individuals;
- intergroup conflicts contribute to group integration, stability, resolution of conflict situations, attracting attention, blurring of group members to the common life of the group.

In studying the problem of conflicts and their nature, determining their causes is considered an important point. The analysis of social and socio-psychological research allows to distinguish the following main causes of conflicts:

- determines the emergence and emergence of existing socio-economic relations in the socio-economic society of today;
- socio-psychological needs, motives and goals of the activities and behaviors of various people;
- differences in behavioral motives and goals in social demographics of people. These differences appear depending on people's gender, age, and ethnicity.

As people pay attention to changing socio-economic situations, they do so based on their interests and needs. Naturally, giving attention to some of these needs and denying some of them causes social reasons for conflicts. The disparity in the

level of income and purchases between the richest and the poorest, the virtual absence of the middle layers of society, the instability of social, economic and political development inevitably causes conflicts at different levels: between individuals, at the level of the whole society. The instability of society and the level of conflict arise from various factors: a high emotional psychological state against the background of interaction between people, an increase in dissatisfaction with the economic situation and life, an increase in vocal conflict, the transformation of deviant behavior into specific social "norms" (quarrels, racketeering, terrorism, drug addiction, prostitution, etc.), "looking for the culprit" (what should be done and who is to blame?). On the other hand, similar negative psychological factors do not have a good effect on the development of the social, economic and political situation.

Social empowerment is characterized by the following parameters:

a) spread of dissatisfaction with life (price increase, inflation, impoverishment of the shopping basket, fear of personal safety, etc.)

b) loss of confidence in the ruling elite (pessimism in the assessment of the future, increased sense of risk, emergence of an atmosphere of public mental unrest and emotional agitation);

c) emergence of spontaneous mass movements (various conflicts, rallies, demonstrations, strikes).

The main stages of social empowerment are:

1) the background level of social intensity is the norm:

2) the hidden stage of the growth of social conflict - its balancing above the norm or within its limits;

3) the stage of social empowerment, the increase of dissatisfaction and the realization that the situation that has arisen is a conflict;

4) the critical stage of the transition of social protest to a sharp conflict;

5) stage of accelerated development of social conflicts - explosion;

6) the highest development stage of social protest - the culmination of the dispute;

7) such as the stage of social discontent falling to the background level and the end of social conflict.

- Above we touched on the psychological criteria of conflicts, albeit partially. Well, in today's process of globalization, the question arises as to the origin of conflicts between teenagers and how the problems of their elimination are being solved. First of all, it is characteristic to find a solution to the issues of prevention before conflicts arise. During our research, we came to the conclusion that the factors that cause conflicts among young people are characterized as follows:

- changes in culture, art and literature, socio-economic conditions as a result of the development of science and technology;

- due to the expansion of mass media, the level of consciousness of adolescents has increased;

- sufficient awareness of teenagers about world events, laws of nature and society, history;

- acceleration of their physical and mental maturity;

- the problems of transparency, social justice, and democracy are deeply penetrating social life;

- that adolescents have ample opportunities for independent learning, creative thinking, self-management, understanding, evaluation and control.

In modern conditions, psychological research is increasingly included in complex research programs in which representatives of other sciences participate. These programs are created, as a rule, to solve major practical problems. In a complex study with one object under study, there is a division of functions between separate approaches. This kind of research makes it possible to establish connections and dependencies between phenomena of various kinds (for example, physical, physiological, mental, social development of a person, etc.).

The second, most extensive group of methods is empirical methods for obtaining scientific data. This group of methods includes: observation and introspection; experimental methods; psychodiagnostic methods (student work of

various kinds); biographical methods (analysis of the events of a person's life path, documentation, testimonies, etc.).

The third group consists of data processing methods. These methods include quantitative (statistical) and qualitative (differentiation of material by groups, variants, description of cases, both expressing types and variants most fully, and being exceptions) analyzes.

The fourth group is interpretative methods. This includes genetic and structural methods.

The genetic method makes it possible to interpret all the processed research material in terms of developmental characteristics, highlighting the phases, stages, and critical moments in the formation of mental neoplasms.

The structural method establishes "horizontal" structural links between all the studied personality characteristics.

Growth is a process of quantitative changes in the course of improving mental function or an increase in the size of the functional capabilities of individual components or the system as a whole.

The two main meanings of the concept of "growth" are growth as a process (as dynamics) and growth as a result of the process (as statics, as a characteristic of an object).

In practical psychology, growth is more often spoken of as a process, a process of growth. When you read just the word "growth" - most likely, it is not about a specific indicator, not about quantitative changes, but about the process of natural unfolding of internal potential. For example, personal growth is an increase in the potential of the individual, which occurs as a result of the natural unfolding in a person of what is inherent in him by nature or has become his second nature.

At the same time, there is an important addition: they talk about growth only with something healthy in mind. If the body weight of a dystrophic increases, they say not about growth, but about the fact that the patient is on the mend.

Growth curve - a curve describing the dependence of the logarithm of the number of living cells on time during culture growth on a non-replaceable medium.

Maturation. The maturational approach to development has dominated psychology for quite some time. It is customary to refer to biological maturation all processes that spontaneously occur under the influence of endogenously programmed, i.e. hereditarily determined and internally controlled growth impulses. These processes include physical changes that are important for mental development - the maturation of the brain, nervous and muscular systems, endocrine glands, etc. Based on the psychophysical unity of man, i.e. connections between somatic and mental processes, biologically oriented models of development represented mental development as an internally regulated process of maturation.

We usually talk about maturation when past experience, learning or exercise (exogenous factors) do not affect (or have an insignificant effect) on the nature of the changes taking place. Along with the restriction of external conditions of development, a number of signs are distinguished that indicate the presence of maturation processes: 1) the similarity of occurrence and course; 2) occurrence at a strictly defined age; 3) catching up; 4) irreversibility.

Differentiation - separation of parts from the whole, necessary for conscious access to psychological functions. Undifferentiated thinking cannot think separately from other functions, that is, sensation or feeling, or intuition is always mixed with it - in the same way, undifferentiated feeling is mixed with sensations and fantasies, as, for example, in the sexualization (Freud) of feeling and thinking in neurosis. Differentiation consists in the isolation of one function from other functions and in the isolation of its individual parts from each other.

Direction is impossible without differentiation, because the direction of a function, or correspondingly its directionality, rests on its isolation and on the exclusion of everything that does not belong together. Differentiation is both a natural process of mental growth and a conscious psychological event - it is necessary for the process of individuation. Centralization is the degree to which an organization concentrates its operational capabilities and decision-making process to a limited number of business units or employees. Centralization, as can be seen from what has been said, is closely related to the degree of formalization of the

structure, and in many respects is determined by it. It is determined and measured through the organization of the management decision-making function. The more this function is concentrated at the highest level, the greater the centralization. On the contrary, the more decision-making freedom other than the highest levels have, the higher the decentralization. The main features of "centralization - decentralization" are therefore the following indicators:

the number of decisions made at lower levels of management;

Centralization improves the control and coordination of specialized independent functions, reduces the number and extent of erroneous decisions made by less experienced managers. Strong centralized control avoids a situation in which some departments of the organization grow and develop at the expense of others or the organization as a whole. Centralized management makes it possible to more economically and easily use the experience and knowledge of the staff of the central administrative body. the amount of control over the work of subordinates.

Concepts of Social Differentiation - in sociology, the concept of social differentiation was first applied by G. Spencer, who borrowed it from biology. Spencer, using numerous examples, demonstrated the process of differentiation of differences that are not connected to the system, the sides of the social life and on this basis proclaimed it a universal direction of societies evolution. P. Sorokin used this concept in a similar way. In structural sociology, the term "differentiation" began to be used as a synonym for the word "difference" and applied ch.arr. for the classification of roles, statuses, institutes and organizations according to various criteria. S. North formulated 4 main criteria for social differentiation: by function, by rank, by culture and by interests. In my understanding of social differentiation functionalists proceed from the fact that any social. A system can only exist if it performs certain vital functions: adaptation to the environment, setting goals, regulation of internal conflicts (integration), etc. Personal and family ties are increasingly giving way to impersonal specialized material relations between people. L.A. Sedov.

Learning - (learning, teaching) - the process of acquiring by the subject of new ways of implementing behavior and activities, fixing and / or modifying them. The change in psychological structures that occurs as a result of this process provides an opportunity for further improvement of activity.

There are three main learning theories:

- the theory of classical conditioning by I.P. Pavlova;
- operant conditioning theory B.F. Skinner;
- A. Bandura's theory of social learning.

There are different concepts of learning. In classical Pavlovian conditioning, subjects begin to give the same response to different stimuli. In Skinner's operant learning, a behavioral act is formed due to the presence or absence of reinforcement of one of the many possible responses. Both of these concepts do not explain how new behavior occurs. A. Bandura believed that reward and punishment are not enough to teach new behavior. Children acquire new behavior by imitating the model. Learning through observation, imitation and identification is the third form of learning. One of the manifestations of imitation is identification - a process in which a person borrows thoughts, feelings or actions from another person acting as a model. Imitation leads to the fact that the child can imagine himself in the place of the model, experience sympathy, complicity, sympathy for this person.

They used concepts such as learning, motivation, driving forces, incentives, mental inhibition, which denoted invisible behavior. According to the eminent learning theorist Clark Hallaety, concepts are scientific insofar as they can be defined in terms of observable operations.

Imprinting or imprinting is a specific form of learning in ethology and psychology; fixation in their memory of signs of objects during the formation or correction of innate behavioral acts. Objects can be parental individuals, brothers and sisters, future sexual partners, food objects (including prey animals), constant enemies, characteristic features of the usual habitat. Imprinting occurs in a strictly defined period of life (usually in childhood and adolescence), and its consequences are most often irreversible.

The most studied and demonstrative form of imprinting is the “following reaction” of mature chicks or young mammals after their parents and one after another. The term was proposed by Konrad Lorenz, who discovered the phenomenon of imprinting while studying greylag geese. Due to a mistranslation into English, this phenomenon is sometimes referred to as "duckling syndrome".

Sensitivity - the ability to feel, which is often assumed and where, strictly speaking, we can only talk about excitability. Sensitive - tangible, perceived by the senses (the opposite is intelligible);

Initially, the concept of a critical period was introduced in embryology to designate time periods characterized by increased sensitivity to the action of factors that go beyond the boundaries of the physiological norm. During intrauterine development, at strictly defined moments, each organ undergoes critical stages of differentiation. A harmful effect on the embryo leads to a selective disturbance in the development of precisely that organ that is in the stage of the most intensive formation. Thus, the critical period in the full sense of the word should be called the period of time when the organism must experience normative influences, and this is a condition for its further full development. Changes during the critical period are irreversible, as a result of which the structure and function acquire a complete form that is not sensitive to modifying influences at a later age.

The above situations directly affect the psychology of teenagers and have a specific effect on the specifics of conflicts observed in them. It is one of the urgent issues of our time to research this uniqueness, to study the conflicts observed in teenagers based on these situations.

Used literature

1. Nikandrov V.V. Methodological basic psychology. Uchebnoe posobie. SPb: Rech, 2008 – 235 p.
2. Psychological diagnosis. Uchebnik dlya VUZov/ Pod ed. M.K. Akimovoy, K.M. Gurevicha. - SPb.: Peter, 2005.- 652 p.

3. Heydarov F.I. Motivation of educational activity. - Tashkent: Science, 2005. - 122 p.

4. Goziev E. Psychology: (Adolescent Psychology): Ped. Study guide for students of universities and colleges. - Tashkent: Teacher, 1994

1. Muhammadjanovna, Rakhimova Feruzakhon. "THE SYSTEM OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF FUTURE EDUCATORS THROUGH PERSONCENTERED EDUCATION." World Bulletin of Social Sciences 7 (2022): 75-77.

2. Mirzaeva, Farokhat, et al. "IMPROVING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS BASED ON A PEDAGOGICAL INNOVATIVE APPROACH." PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology 17.6 (2020): 8919-8926.

3. Muhammadjonovna, Rakhimova Feruzakhon. "Improvement Of The System Of Formation And Development Of Creative Activity Of Future Educators On The Basis Of PersonalityOriented Education." Eurasian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences 3 (2021): 32-36.

4. Mukhammadjonovna, Rakhimova Feruzakhon. "Pedagogical and psychological features of the formation of the creative activity of future teachers through personality-oriented education." ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal 11.4 (2021): 1053-1056.

5. Raximova, Feruzaxon Muxammadjonovna. "PROBLEMS OF ESTABLISHING AND STRENGTHENING THE MATERIAL BASE OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION ORGANIZATION." Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире 4-7 (2021): 51-56.

6. Esonova, M. A. "Improving the Preparation of Children for School Education on the Basis of the Curriculum in the Preschool System." Middle European Scientific Bulletin 18 (2021): 24-26.

7. Akilovna, Esonova Maloxatxon. "THE COMPETENCE OF THE EDUCATOR IN THE APPLICATION OF TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE ORGANIZATION OF HEALTH CARE WORK FOR CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AGE." INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE &

INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429 11.04 (2022): 147-150.

8. Akilovna, Esonova Malokhat. "Developing correct pronunciation in students through the formation of monologue speech in preschool education." INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DISCOURSE ON INNOVATION, INTEGRATION AND EDUCATION 2.2 (2021): 73-75.

9. Эсонова, М. А. "ТАЪЛИМ МАЗМУНИНИНГ ИНТЕГРАЛ ХАРАКТЕРИ." Сборники конференций НИЦ Социосфера. No. 6. Vedecko vydavatelске centrum Sociosfera-CZ sro, 2016.

10. ЭСОНОВА, МАЛОХАТ АКИЛОВНА. "ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ НРАВСТВЕННОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ У ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА." Юность и Знания-Гарантия Успеха-2015. 2015.

11. Эсонова, Малохат Акиловна. "Роль речевой коммуникации в педагогическом мастерстве." Теория и практика современных гуманитарных и естественных наук. 2014.

12. Эсонова, Малохат Акиловна. "НАРОДНАЯ ПЕДАГОГИКА КАК ВЫСШАЯ СОЦИАЛЬНАЯ ЦЕННОСТЬ ДУХОВНОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ НАРОДА." Исследование инновационного потенциала общества и формирование направлений его стратегического развития. 2014.

13. ЭСОНОВА, МАЛОХАТ АКИЛОВНА, and ШАХНОЗА АБДУГАФАРОВИЧ ИБРАГИМОВА. "ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ." Будущее науки-2014. 2014.

14. Akilovna, Esonova Maloxat. "METHODS OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGUES." INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429 11.05 (2022): 228-232.

15. Akilovna, Esonova Malohat, and Boymirzayeva Fotima. "MODERN APPROACHES TO CHILDREN'S INTELLECTUAL DEVELOPMENT." INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE &

INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429 11.05 (2022): 233-237.

16. Nazirova, Guzal, Dilfuza Yulchiboeva, and Oxunjon Khaydarov. "The Main Factors of Formation and Development of Professional Competence of Teachers of Preschool Educational Organizations." REVISTA GEINTEC-GESTAO INOVACAO E TECNOLOGIAS 11.3 (2021): 1698-1708.

17. Nazirova, Guzal M. "Features of Organization Pedagogical Process in Preschool Educational Institutions." Eastern European Scientific Journal 1 (2017).

18. Djuraev, R. X., S. T. Turgunov, and G. M. Nazirova. "Pedagogy." T.: O'zPFITI (2013).

19. Назирова, Г. М. "РАЗВИТИЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ ВОСПИТАТЕЛЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЙ НА ОСНОВЕ СИСТЕМНОГО ПОДХОДА." Актуальные проблемы современной науки 4 (2014): 96-99.

20. Назирова, Г. М. "Особенности процесса деятельности воспитателей дошкольных образовательных учреждений." Вопросы гуманитарных наук 4 (2014): 61-63.

21. Guzal, Nazirova. "MAKTABGACHA KATTA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA IJTIMOIIY ONGNI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK-PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI." Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal 1.5 (2022): 35-39.

22. Guzal, Nazirova. "PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE FORMATION OF SOCIAL CONSCIOUSNESS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN." Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal 1.5 (2022): 40-46.

23. Malikovna, Nazirova Guzal. "MODERN APPROACHES TO THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM OF PRESCHOOL ORGANIZATIONS." INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876 16.06 (2022): 76-81.